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Offline simulation tool

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Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
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Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	Executive Summary	4
2.	Introduction	4
3.	Availability	5
4.	Uptake	6
5.	The FABM Offline Simulator	6
	Structure	6
	Transport engines	7
	Domains and clustering	8
	Performance	8
	Future development	9
6.	Clustering methods	10
	SOM classification of the Arctic Ocean biogeochemical model output	10
	Alternative classification methods: k-shape	12
7.	Worked example: Arctic MFC	13
	Workflow	17
	Results	17
8.	References	20
9.	Appendix: example scripts	22
	download.py	22
	preprocess.py	23
	run.py	24

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the functionality and availability of the FABM Offline Simulator (fabmos) software package developed within NECCTON. This package provides a set of new biogeochemical/ecological model testbeds for the NECCTON interlinked modelling framework. The testbeds improve upon existing ones (box models, water column models) by better representing spatial variability and the impact of horizontal transport on biogeochemical/ecological variables. At the same time, the new testbeds maintain good computational performance, enabling a model year to be simulated in minutes to one hour on a single workstation. An example is included to demonstrate how an efficient testbed for an existing Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS) Monitoring and Forecasting Centre (MFC) domain can be set up. We envisage the new fabmos package to be particularly useful for the development and parameterisation of new process descriptions within NECCTON.

Introduction

Operational simulations with coupled physical-biogeochemical models, such as used in the Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS), endeavour to represent a maximum of spatial detail in order to resolve the scales that most stakeholders are interested in. The high-resolution 3D model configurations that this requires are computationally expensive to run: even on High Performance Computing (HPC) systems with 100s of processor cores, a multi-decade simulation may take weeks or even months to complete. Thus, there is little to no scope to run extensive experiments with these full setups, for instance, to support rigorous parameter sensitivity analysis, parameter calibration, or to determine the equilibrium state of the models after 1000s of years of simulations.

Sensitivity analysis and calibration experiments are indispensable when developing new process models or parameterisations, as undertaken in NECCTON. However, as these studies require 100s to 1000s of simulations, they tend to resort to fast-running models with greatly reduced spatial detail, for instance, 0D box models or 1D water columns. In these testbeds it is difficult, if not impossible, to adequately characterise the impact of transport processes, notably that of water movement and (horizontal) mixing processes. As a result, a parametrisation carefully calibrated in 0D or 1D setting may perform quite differently when placed in high resolution 3D models. This can cause or amplify mismatches between model and observations and thus reduce the quality of model results. Since the cause of this is the lack of spatial detail in the testbeds, this issue persists even if the exact same biogeochemical model code and parameter set is used in the high-resolution model and in the testbeds, as ensured in NECCTON by its interlinked modelling framework. There is, therefore, a need for new model testbeds of intermediate complexity, striking a balance between the fast runtime of 0D/1D models, and the spatial detail and faithful representation of transports of operation high-resolution models.

The FABM Offline Simulator (fabmos) has been developed in NECCTON to fill the gap between 0D/1D model testbeds and operational-quality high-resolution 3D models. fabmos is an open-

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

source Python-based software package for efficient biogeochemical model simulations. It builds on the Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models (FABM; Bruggeman & Bolding, 2014) to integrate all biogeochemical and ecological models developed within the NECCTON interlinked modelling framework. In order to deliver both good performance and adequate spatial detail, fabmos focuses on intermediate-complexity representations of the spatial environment, such as:

- 3D simulations with coarse horizontal and vertical resolution, for instance, global models with 2.8° horizontal resolution and 15 vertical layers
- 3D simulations with limited number (10-100) of horizontal regions or biogeographical provinces, identified by clustering methods, and high-resolution representation of the water column (e.g. 50-100 vertical layers)
- 2D simulations with high-resolution horizontal grids (e.g. the original CMEMS grid) but no vertical detail, for instance, to model benthic sediments, fauna and/or macrophytes.

The unifying feature of these model configurations that they are forced to some degree by existing outputs of past hydrodynamic model simulations. Hence, they are “offline” biogeochemical simulations: parts of the physics – at the very least the horizontal transports – are prescribed, not calculated, at the time the biogeochemical model runs. This enables high performance: it is typically feasible to run multi-annual fabmos-based simulations in minutes to hours, on a standard computer laptop or workstation. This report summarises the features of fabmos, its availability, and describes an example of how it can be used specifically to obtain efficient, reduced-spatial-complexity representation of high-resolution models as used operationally within CMEMS and NECCTON.

Availability

The source code of fabmos is open source (licensed under the GNU General Public License v2.0) and available on GitHub:

<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/fabmos>

Prebuilt, readily-installable fabmos packages for Windows, Mac and Linux are available through Anaconda:

<https://anaconda.org/conda-forge/fabmos>

fabmos integrates the latest version of the FABM+ distribution (<https://github.com/fabm-model/fabm-plus>), which combines FABM and many externally maintained biogeochemical models. These already include ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016), BFM (Vichi et al., 2020), PISCES (Aumont et al., 2015), (Yumruktepe et al., 2022) and ERGOM (Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research, 2015), all used within CMEMS and NECCTON. The standard version of these models is included with the fabmos source code (as git submodules) and in the prebuilt packages on Anaconda. Developers of biogeochemical models can readily integrate their custom codebases with fabmos at compile time.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Detailed installation and compilation instructions for fabmos are provided on the wiki:

<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/fabmos/wiki>

The wiki also includes a user guide that describes common usage patterns, e.g., for specifying model input, output, restarts, and parallelized simulation. This section will be expanded over the lifetime of NECCTON in response to user/partner queries and requests.

Uptake

Since its initial development (first commit to the public codebase in August 2023), fabmos has seen significant uptake within NECCTON and beyond. Within NECCTON, it has been used to simulate benthic biogeochemistry (with ERSEM), coupled biogeochemistry and fish (PISCES and SEAPODYM-LMTL), and high biodiversity configurations of plankton models (BFM).

Outside NECCTON, it has been taken up within the OceanICU project (<https://ocean-icu.eu/>) as the foundation to implement a dedicated transport engine (the Transport Matrix Method) for long-term global simulations. Additionally, fabmos will provide the simulation backbone for a study on the fate of fish food additives in aquaculture, commissioned by the European Food Safety Authority.

Finally, fabmos was used extensively in the marine biogeochemical and ecosystem modelling workshop organized jointly by NECCTON and OceanICU as part of the 2024 Advances in Marine Ecosystem Modelling Research conference (<https://www.amemr.com/>). It will again be used in an upcoming NECCTON-aligned workshop exploring the latest developments in FABM (<https://github.com/fabm-model/fabm/wiki/workshop>).

The FABM Offline Simulator

Structure

Fabmos is a software package written in Python. It builds on several co-developed Python packages for dedicated functionality:

- pygetm: a flexible, extensive for codebase for coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical 3D simulations (<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/getm-rewrite>)
- pygotm: the Python interface to the general Ocean Turbulence Model (GOTM; Burchard et al., 1999) (<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/pygotm>)
- pyfabm: the Python interface to the Framework for Aquatic Biogeochemical Models (<https://github.com/fabm-model/fabm>)
- awex: a Python package for calculating air-water exchange of heat and momentum (<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/awex>)

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

In turn, these packages build on widely used Python packages such as NumPy (<https://numpy.org/>), xarray (<https://xarray.dev/>), SciPy (<https://scipy.org/>) and mpi4py (<https://mpi4py.readthedocs.io/>).

In particular, fabmos makes extensive use of the “pygetm” package, using it for all input and output, time integration, numerical schemes for transport, and biogeochemistry (i.e., FABM integration). To make this possible, pygetm and fabmos were developed in tandem where needed, with corrections and extensions made to the pygetm codebase specifically to support fabmos. For instance, pygetm was extended to handle the various different grids that fabmos supports (e.g. 1D horizontal to represent clustered domains, flipped vertical axes) and to support prescribed sea ice coverage.

Figure 5.1. Modules of the fabmos codebase and its dependencies.

Transport engines

Fabmos currently includes three transport engines:

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

- null: no transport is applied. All quantities (pelagic as well as benthic) thus remain in their model grid cell and change only due to the local biogeochemical/ecological processes, rates of which are calculated within FABM. This can be appropriate for simulations of benthic processes (e.g. benthic fauna), which can then be forced with time/space-varying pelagic conditions derived from observations or earlier model results.
- gotm: a full water column simulation (coupled vertical hydrodynamics and biogeochemistry) with the General Ocean Turbulence Model (GOTM) is run at every horizontal grid cell (or cluster). Mixing between these water columns is applied at every time step based on the depth-integrated transport between cells. This transport is inferred from pre-run hydrodynamic model simulations and represented by a connectivity matrix. The gotm transport engine is typically used to represent high vertical detail (typically 50-150 layers) in a limited number of horizontal cells/clusters/patches.
- tmm (developed within <https://ocean-icu.eu/>): an implementation of the Transport Matrix Method (TMM; Khatiwala, 2007), typically used for long-term global simulations under climatological forcing

Domains and clustering

The first step in setting up fabmos simulations is to load a domain, which specifies the geographical region, horizontal discretization (number and extent of grid cells) and bottom depth (bathymetry). This information can come from a wide variety of data sources and is fed into the model using standard numpy/xarray data types. Examples are provided to show how domains are loaded from NetCDF files, and more specifically, from NEMO topo files.

Fabmos includes built-in support for reducing horizontal complexity through incorporation of clustering information. It can take the output of a horizontal clustering algorithm (a matrix specifying the cluster id for every original grid cell) to collapse the original 2D horizontal domain into a 1D representation, with each new cell representing a single cluster. Clustering algorithms suitable for this purpose were developed and tested for this purpose within NECCON, as described in upcoming section 6.

Fabmos includes a number of methods to facilitate working with clustered domains, which among other support averaging of horizontally explicit inputs (e.g., meteorology, initial conditions) over the individual clusters, the calculation of connectivity matrices (transport between clusters) from spatially resolved (3D) water velocities, and the splitting of clusters that are not spatially contiguous (i.e., that consist of multiple groups of grid cells that are not connected spatially). This functionality is located in module `fabmos.input.cluster`.

Performance

The runtime of fabmos simulations is dependent on the horizontal and spatial detail that is represented, the complexity of the biogeochemical or ecological model (notably the number of tracers), the transport engine used, the time step chosen, the amount of output saved, and the computer and number of cores that the simulation is run on. Thus, it is not possible to give generalized estimates of runtime. An example of runtimes is given in table 5.1.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Table 5.1. Examples of fabmos runtimes for a range of configurations. Runtimes were measured on a workstation with an Intel Core i7-10700 CPU (8 cores) and 32 GB memory.

domain	resolution	biogeochemistry	transport engine	runtime (seconds per simulated year)	
				serial (1 core)	parallel (5 cores)
global	2.8°, 15 layers, $\Delta t=12$ h	MOPS (Kriest & Oeschlies, 2015)	tmm	48	29
global	2.8°, 15 layers, $\Delta t_{\text{transport}}=12$ h, $\Delta t_{\text{BGC}}=1$ h	ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016)	tmm	1413	542
CMEMS North-West Shelf (full grid)	7 km, 1 layer, $\Delta t=1$ h	ERSEM (Butenschön et al., 2016) – benthos only	null (no transport)	2607	1372
CMEMS Arctic (clustered)	12 clusters, 50 layers	ECOSMO (Yumruktepe et al., 2022)	gotm	41	NA

Future development

Fabmos will be developed further in several directions within the remainder of NECCON, and in other projects that build on fabmos:

- A “forced” transport engine will build on the concept of a connectivity matrix for horizontal mixing between cells (clusters) as described here, and model the vertical transport within each cell by applying prescribed vertical diffusivities (as opposed to the gotm transport engine, which calculates these dynamically through and turbulence modelling, forced by meteorological conditions). This transport engine will enable model

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

simulations in which all hydrodynamics (velocities and mixing) are fully prescribed, for instance, by downloaded outputs of CMEMS hindcasts. It is worth noting that this will require vertical diffusivities to be available from the Copernicus Marine Data Store for all MFCs, which is not the case now.

- Support for connectivity matrices, as used by the gotm transport engine and in the upcoming worked example (section 7), will be expanded to support depth-explicit connectivity as well as the current depth-averaged connectivity. This will also enable the reconstruction of vertical velocities from the local net water import in every layer.
- For cells/clusters at external (open) model boundaries, a mechanism will be introduced to prescribe an external tracer concentration, to be taken into account when the cell/cluster experiences a net influx of water over that external boundary.
- In the task T3.4 in NECCTON, the performance of NECCTON biogeochemical models will be assessed and improved and an experimental GPU implementation of the NECCTON interlinked modelling framework will be developed and tested specifically within fabmos. These developments are expected to lead to improvements in computational efficiency, and thus reduce the simulation runtime (e.g., table 5.1)

Clustering methods

SOM classification of the Arctic Ocean biogeochemical model output

The concept of ecoregions is based on the observation that large geographical regions are characterized by coherent physical forcing and environmental conditions, which shape ecosystem structure and function (Longhurst et al., 1995). In this study, we applied the unsupervised classification method, self-organizing map (SOM; Kohonen, 2001), to cluster the Arctic Ocean model domain into ecoregions based on a set of physical, biogeochemical and geospatial parameters derived from ocean model outputs. This approach closely follows Fendereski et al. (2014).

The input data for the SOM classification comes from daily mean outputs of a hindcast run of the TP2 ocean model, conducted over a 10-year period from 2007 to 2016. TP2 is a coupled ocean-ice-biogeochemistry (HYCOM-CICE-ECOSMO) model configuration with a horizontal resolution of approximately 17 km and 50 vertical layers. For further model details, see Yumruktepe et al. (2022). The interannual daily mean data from the hindcast are averaged to generate climatological data and further processed to derive annual, winter, and summer means. The winter mean is defined as the temporal average of January, February, and March (JFM), and the summer mean as the average of July, August, and September (JAS). Seasonal change data are then obtained by subtracting the winter mean from the summer mean.

We selected five model variables—sea surface temperature (SST), sea surface salinity (SSS), mixed layer depth (MLD), sea surface chlorophyll-a concentration (CHL), and photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) at the sea surface—as season-dependent parameters. Additionally, three static parameters—day of the year when surface chlorophyll-a reaches its first maximum (MAXD), latitudes (LAT), and bathymetry (TOPO)—were included. In total, 13 parameters were

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

used: MSST, MSSS, MMLD, MCHL, MPAR, DSST, DSSS, DMLD, DCHL, DPAR, MAXD, LATS, and TOPO, as summarized in Table 6.1. Note that MAXD is not directly output by the model but is a diagnostic parameter derived from the daily time series of CHL, introduced to capture phytoplankton phenology.

All parameters were normalized to a standard deviation of 1.0 and concatenated into a 13-dimensional vector for each model grid. The SOM topology map was defined as a 4x3 rectangular grid, classifying the TP2 ocean model domain into 12 subregions (SOM classes). SOM classification was performed using the Python SOM package, `sklearn_som` (<https://github.com/rileypsmith/sklearn-som>). After classification, spatial smoothing was applied to the class distributions to eliminate small or narrow subregions. A sample of the final SOM classes, mapped over the TP2 model domain, is shown in Figure 1. Python package including the model data preprocessing and the SOM classification can be found in the git repository: https://github.com/nansencenter/NECCTON_WP3/tree/main/TP2SOM.

Table 6.1. List of model parameters for SOM classification.

Parameter Name	Parameter Definition
MSST/DSST	Annual mean (M) / Seasonal change (D) of sea surface temperature
MSSS/DSSS	Annual mean (M) / Seasonal change (D) of sea surface salinity
MMLD/DMLD	Annual mean (M) / Seasonal change (D) of mixed layer depth
MCHL/DCHL	Annual mean (M) / Seasonal change (D) of sea surface chlorophyll-a concentration
MPAR/DPAR	Annual mean (M) / Seasonal change (D) of photosynthesis available radiation at sea surface
MAXD	Day of year when sea surface chlorophyll-a concentration reaches its first maximum.
LATS	latitudes
TOPO	bathymetry

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

TP2 som classes: 2007-2016 (trial 82) smoothed

Figure 6.1. Result of SOM classification of the Arctic model domain using 12 classes.

Alternative classification methods: k-shape

An alternative algorithm to perform unsupervised clustering is the k-shape algorithm (Paparrizos & Gravano, 2016). K-shape is a form of dynamic time warping (DTW) and is designed to work on time-series data, using a version of the cross-correlation measure for defining cluster centroids that considers the shape of time series data. This allows multivariate temporal data to be used as inputs.

For comparison with the SOM approach, the same source dataset is used with daily mean outputs over a 10-year period from 2007 to 2016. The surface fields for nine variables are used in the clustering (temperature, salinity, chlorophyll (large phytoplankton, small phytoplankton, coccoliths), shortwave fluxes, PAR, SI coverage and SI thickness), with each variable normalised to a standard deviation of 1. For ease the data is averaged into a one-year climatology and reshaped into a three-dimensional array (Ngrid x 365 x 9). No post-processing has been applied.

A sample of the class map for 6 clusters is seen in Figure 6.2. The results show encouraging similarity with the SOM method, with clear features identifiable between the two.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

The python code used to generate the clusters, including all preprocessing is publicly available in a git repository: <https://github.com/pmlmodelling/ModelViz>.

Figure 6.2. Result of k-shape classification of the Arctic model domain.

Worked example: Arctic MFC

This section demonstrates how fabmos can be used to obtain an efficient representation of the type of computationally costly high-resolution simulations used in CMEMS and NECCTON. This is demonstrated with a hindcast from the CMEMS Arctic Monitoring Forecasting Centre (MFC), which through clustering (see section 6) is reduced from its original 380×400 horizontal grid to 12 clusters representing similar physical-biogeochemical regimes. Water columns for each of these clusters are then simulated with the gotm transport engine at relatively high vertical detail, using 50 layers zoomed towards the surface using a Generalized Vertical Coordinate parametrisation (Burchard & Bolding, 2002). Continuous mixing between the columns is applied, based on time-varying depth-integrated volume transports between clusters, inferred from the eastward and northward velocity components downloaded from the Copernicus Marine Data Store.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

While developing this example, we encountered a number of challenges that are partially specific to the Arctic MFC. Specifically:

1. As it employs a rotated grid (polar stereographic projection), the eastward/northward velocity fields offered by CMEMS need to be rotated to the model grid before calculating between-cluster connectivity from transports over cell interfaces.
2. As the grid encompasses the North Pole, it covers the full global range in longitude (-180 to 180°), necessitating very large downloads (>120 GB) for forcing datasets offered on regular grids (ERA5 meteorology, CMEMS velocities).
3. As a significant part of the modelled region is ice-covered at any time of the year, a good model representation of sea ice coverage is vital in order to obtain reasonable simulation results. The original sea ice model that fabmos acquired from pygetm is not suitable for this purpose, as this is a rudimentary model that does not account for ice thickness. Therefore, fabmos and pygetm were both extended to support prescribed sea ice coverage, and the modules downloading and interpolating meteorological inputs were extended to handle this.

The various developments needed to overcome these challenges have been incorporated into the fabmos codebase, which thereby improved its general applicability and computational performance, and reduced its data storage needs.

The clustering employed here is based on section 6. It consists of 12 clusters, shown in Fig. 7.1.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Figure 7.1. Arctic SOM-based clustering with 12 clusters (see section 6). The numbers are cluster identifiers, used in subsequent figures.

The gotm transport engine used in this example calculates vertical mixing through turbulence modelling. It is driven by meteorological conditions at the water surface, specifically air temperature, humidity (dewpoint temperature), wind speeds in x- and y-direction, surface air pressure, cloud cover and (specifically in the Arctic MFC) sea ice coverage as an area fraction. These variables were taken from the ERA5 dataset (Hersbach et al., 2023), obtained from the Climate Data Store (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>). The variables were subsequently averaged over each cluster using the standard methods that fabmos provided. Notably, the averaging procedure takes care to preserve the approximate surface input of momentum by averaging wind speed and angle (Grange, 2014); the alternative of individually averaging x- and y-components of the wind would greatly diminish the average wind speed, and thus, energy input to the ocean (Ponte & Rosen, 2004; Zhai, 2013) as well as wind-controlled biogeochemical processes such as air-sea gas exchange (Orr et al., 2017). The downloading and averaging of ERA5 variables across clusters is done as preprocessing step. This produces time series of meteorological forcing per cluster (a NetCDF file) that are read directly during the simulation.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

To initialize, the model requires depth-explicit values of conservative temperature, absolute salinity and all biogeochemical variables represented by the ECOSMO model employed in the Arctic MFC. In this example, GLODAPv2 (Lauvset et al., 2016) is used to infer temperature, salinity, oxygen, total dissolved inorganic carbon, nitrate, phosphate and silicate. The remaining biogeochemical variables (e.g., constituents of plankton and detritus) are left at ECOSMO's default initial value. During preprocessing, the global dataset is downloaded using standard fabmos methods and then interpolated to the original Arctic MFC model grid. The averaging of initial conditions over each cluster is done at runtime.

The connectivity between clusters is inferred from time and space (3D) varying velocities downloaded from the Copernicus Marine Data Store (E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS). Marine Data Store (MDS), 2024). For this purpose, the eastward and northward velocities are interpolated to the interfaces of all grid cells of the original CMEMS domain. They are then rotated to the projected model grid to obtain the velocity perpendicular to each cell interface (thus producing an inward or outward velocity). Fabmos maintains an internal representation of all original cell interfaces that link any pair of clusters. This information is combined with the inward/outward velocities to calculate the total transport ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$) between each pair of clusters. The result is shown in figure 7.2, which shows the relative total inflow/outflow per cluster on the left (equivalent to a relaxation rate) and the flow between pairs of clusters on the right. This is represented by a time-varying connectivity matrix that is saved to NetCDF during preprocessing and read directly during the simulation.

Figure 7.2. Average flow between clusters (see Fig 7.1) for 2015-2020, based on velocities obtained from the CMEMS reanalysis for the Arctic. The left panel shows the relative inflow and outflow for each individual cluster. This can be thought of as the rate at which the cluster value is relaxed towards a blend of the values of other clusters. It is compared to a relaxation rate as employed, for instance, in GOTM (Burchard et al., 1999). The right panel shows the flow between pairs of clusters.

Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Workflow

The workflow for this example consists of four steps:

- Downloading GLODAPv2, ERA5 and CMEMS forcing data (download.py in section 1). This phase takes the longest; currently 12-24 hours. The main bottleneck is the downloading of about 100 GB of ERA5 meteorological data from the Climate Data Store, which uses a queuing system that processes one request (in the case of this example, one year) at a time.
- Preprocessing the data (preprocess.py in section 1). This averages meteorological variables per cluster, regrid the GLODAPv2 dataset to the original Arctic grid, and infers transports between clusters from the CMEMS horizontal velocities. This phase takes about 1 hour to process 6 years of forcing.
- Running the model (run.py in section 1). This takes about 41 seconds per simulated year (see also table 5.1)
- Plotting the outputs. This is done with a Jupyter Notebook (plot.ipynb) included in the repository.

All scripts for download and preprocessing of forcing data, model simulation and a Jupyter notebook for plotting results are available in the arctic-clusters folder of a dedicated repository:

<https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/fabmos-cases>

They are also included verbatim in section 1. The scripts are readily adapted to new domains, as they only require information about the original domain (coordinates, bathymetry), a matrix with cluster identifiers per cell and a choice of any of the biogeochemical/ecological models include in FABM+.

Results

Figures 7.3 and 7.4 show the monthly surface values of temperature and flagellate chlorophyll, respectively, for the 2007-2015 climatology of the high-resolution CMEMS simulation (left) and the 12-cluster testbed simulation (right). In general, both temperature and chlorophyll in the full-resolution and clustered simulations show strong similarities, suggesting that the underlying models in the clustered simulation (GOTM and ECOSMO) operate as intended. Where mismatches do occur, they seem concentrated around the outer edges of the domain (e.g. excessively cold water at the southern Atlantic boundary near the turn of the year). This indicates that planned future developments that improve boundary treatment in the clustered simulation (final part of section 5) have the potential to improve results.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Figure 7.3. Mid-monthly sea surface temperature of the original CMEMS hindcast (climatology 2007-2016; left image of each monthly pair) compared with the sea surface temperature of the clustered simulation with the gotm transport engine (one year: 2015; right image).

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Figure 7.4. Mid-monthly flagellate chlorophyll at the surface of the original CMEMS hindcast (climatology 2007-2016; left image of each monthly pair) compared with the equivalent in the clustered simulation with the gotm transport engine (one year: 2015; right image). The underlying ECOMSO code and parametrisation are identical in both.

Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

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Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

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Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

Appendix: example scripts

This scripts below are available from the arctic-clusters folder of the <https://github.com/BoldingBruggeman/fabmos-cases> repository.

download.py

```
import os.path
import copernicusmarine
import pygetm.input.glodap
import pygetm.input.era5
import run

TARGET_DIR = "." # Target dir for downloads (~120 GB!)

MINYEAR = 2015
MAXYEAR = 2020

if __name__ == "__main__":
    domain = run.get_domain(cluster=False)

    # GLODAP initial conditions (global)
    pygetm.input.glodap.download_and_process(os.path.join(TARGET_DIR, "glodap.nc"))

    # ERA5 meteorology (lat-lon rectangle encompassing original domain)
    lon = domain.lon[1::2, 1::2]
    lat = domain.lat[1::2, 1::2]
    era_year2path = pygetm.input.era5.get(
        lon.min(),
        lon.max(),
        lat.min(),
        lat.max(),
        MINYEAR,
        MAXYEAR,
        variables=("t2m", "d2m", "u10", "v10", "sp", "tcc", "siconc"),
        target_dir=os.path.join(TARGET_DIR, "era5"),
    )

    # CMEMS currents to infer cluster connectivity (entire Arctic MFC)
    copernicusmarine.subset(
        dataset_id="cmems_mod_arc_phy_my_topaz4_P1M",
        variables=["vxo", "vyo"],
        start_datetime=f"{MINYEAR}-01-01T00:00:00",
        end_datetime=f"{MAXYEAR + 1}-01-01T00:00:00",
        output_filename="flow.nc",
        output_directory=os.path.join(TARGET_DIR, "cmems"),
    )
```


Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

preprocess.py

```

import os.path
import glob
import logging

import fabmos.input.cluster
import pygetm.input.glodap

import run
from download import TARGET_DIR as DATA_DIR

if __name__ == "__main__":
    logging.basicConfig(level=logging.INFO)
    logger = logging.getLogger()

    domain = run.get_domain(cluster=True)

    # Interpolate GLODAP to the original model grid, but wait with averaging
    # over clusters until runtime, as we need the vertical layer distribution
    pygetm.input.glodap.regrid(
        os.path.join(DATA_DIR, "glodap.nc"),
        domain.full_lon,
        domain.full_lat,
        "glodap_ip.nc",
        clamp=True,
        logger=logger,
    )

    # Calculate transport between clusters from CMEMS velocities
    FLOW_FILE = os.path.join(DATA_DIR, "cmems", "flow.nc")
    u = fabmos.input.from_nc(FLOW_FILE, "vx0")
    v = fabmos.input.from_nc(FLOW_FILE, "vy0")
    fabmos.input.cluster.get_connectivity(
        domain, u, v, "connections.nc", periodic_lon=True, logger=logger
    )

    # Average ERA5 per cluster (special treatment of wind components u10 and
    # v10 to preserve average wind speed)
    ERA_FILES = os.path.join(DATA_DIR, "era5", "era5_?????.nc")
    for infile in glob.glob(ERA_FILES):
        outfile = f"{os.path.basename(infile)[: -3]}.nc"
        logger.info(f"Averaging {infile} and saving to {outfile}...")
        fabmos.input.cluster.average(
            domain,
            infile,
            outfile,
            chunksize=24 * 20,
            averager=fabmos.input.cluster.average_uv,
            periodic_lon=True,
            logger=logger,
        )

```


Project	NECCTON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

run.py

```

import datetime
import os.path

import netCDF4
import numpy as np

import fabmos
import fabmos.transport.gotm
import fabmos.input.cluster
import pygetm

DOMAIN_FILE = "smoothed_ecoregion_6_iteration.nc"
SPLIT_CLUSTERS = False # True

def get_domain(cluster: bool) -> fabmos.domain.Domain:
    # Estimate hydrodynamic bottom roughness from HYCOM's drag
    C_D = 0.003 # drag coefficient
    h_bot = 10.0 # thickness of bottom layer (HYCOM manual section 4.1.2)
    z0b = 0.5 * h_bot / (np.exp(0.4 / np.sqrt(C_D)) - 1.0)

    with netCDF4.Dataset(DOMAIN_FILE) as nc:
        depth = nc["depth"]
        ny, nx = depth.shape
        masked = np.ma.getmaskarray(depth)
        domain = fabmos.domain.Domain(
            nx,
            ny,
            lon=nc["longitude"],
            lat=nc["latitude"],
            H=depth,
            z0=z0b,
            mask=np.where(masked, 0, 1),
            coordinate_type=fabmos.CoordinateType.IJ,
        )
        clusters = np.ma.array(nc["ecoregion"], mask=masked)
    if not cluster:
        return domain
    if SPLIT_CLUSTERS:
        clusters = fabmos.input.cluster.split(clusters)
    return fabmos.domain.compress_clusters(domain, clusters)

if __name__ == "__main__":
    domain = get_domain(cluster=True)

    sim = fabmos.transport.gotm.Simulator(
        domain,
        fabm="fabm.yaml",
        gotm="gotm.yaml",
        ice=pygetm.ice.Prescribed(),
        vertical_coordinates=fabmos.vertical_coordinates.GVC(
            nz=50, ddl=0.5, ddu=0.75, Dgamma=40.0
        ),
        connectivity=fabmos.input.from_nc("connections.nc", "exchange"),
    )

    # Meteorology
    # fmt: off
    METEO_FILE = "era5_?????.nc"
    sim.airsea.u10.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "u10"), on_grid=True)
    sim.airsea.v10.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "v10"), on_grid=True)

```


Project	NECCON No 101081273	Deliverable	3.2
Dissemination	Public	Nature	Other (software)
Date	31 January 2025	Version	2.0

```

sim.airsea.t2m.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "t2m") - 273.15, on_grid=True)
sim.airsea.d2m.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "d2m") - 273.15, on_grid=True)
sim.airsea.sp.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "sp"), on_grid=True)
sim.airsea.tcc.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "tcc"), on_grid=True)
sim.ice.ice.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(METEO_FILE, "siconc"), on_grid=True)

# Ensure T&S are valid in cells that fall outside active domain,
# but where FABM/ECOSMO are still evaluated (e.g. inactive part of last subdomain)
# This is needed to prevent carbonate chemistry errors.
sim.temp.values.fill(5.0)
sim.salt.values.fill(35.0)

# Initial conditions for temperature, salinity and biogeochemistry
GLODAP_FILE = "glodap_ip.nc"
assert os.path.isfile(GLODAP_FILE), "First run `preprocess.py`"
sim.temp.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "ct"), on_grid=True)
sim.salt.set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "sa"), on_grid=True)
rho = fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "density") * 0.001 # in kg L-1
sim["ECO_no3"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "N03") * rho * 6.625 * 12.01,
on_grid=True)
sim["ECO_pho"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "P04") * rho * 106.0 * 12.01,
on_grid=True)
sim["ECO_sil"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "silicate") * rho * 6.625 * 12.01,
on_grid=True)
sim["ECO_oxo"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "oxygen") * rho, on_grid=True)
sim["CO2_TA"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "TAlk") * rho, on_grid=True)
sim["CO2_c"].set(fabmos.input.from_nc(GLODAP_FILE, "TCO2") * rho, on_grid=True)
# fmt: on

# Light attenuation based on Jerlov water type
# (https://doi.org/10.1029/JC091iC05p06642)
# Time/space varying values could be used instead by calling .set(...)
# on sim.radiation.A, sim.radiation.kc1, sim.radiation.kc2
sim.radiation.jerlov_type = pygetm.radiation.Jerlov.Type_III

# Atmospheric pCO2
sim.fabm.get_dependency("mole_fraction_of_carbon_dioxide_in_air").set(401.0)

# Configure output
out = sim.output_manager.add_netcdf_file(
    "gotm-arctic.nc", interval=datetime.timedelta(days=1), sync_interval=None
)
out.request("temp", "salt", "nuh", "ice", *sim.fabm.state_variables)

# Simulate
sim.start(
    datetime.datetime(2015, 1, 1),
    3600.0,
    report=datetime.timedelta(days=10),
    report_totals=datetime.timedelta(days=365),
)
while sim.time < datetime.datetime(2020, 12, 31):
    sim.advance()
sim.finish()

```